

Rurbanization in Telangana

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ABSTRACT

As per Census of India statistics, the rural population in India, stands at 833 million, constituting almost 68% of the total population. Telangana is the 29th and newly formed state of India. It has a vast rural population which has a lot of scope in the development of rural areas. The government of Telangana has proposed 18 rurban clusters to the Indian government. The rurban clusters include villages with a population of 25000-50000 in plain areas and 5000-15000 in tribal, hilly and desert areas. The funding of the project will be through various schemes of the Government. The project will be implemented through the Public Private Partnership (PPP) model.

Keywords: Rural, Cluster, Hilly, Tribal, Desert area, Public Private Partnership (PPP) model

INTRODUCTION

Rurbanization aims to create a cluster of villages and provide urban amenities to the people living within that cluster. Thus, the aim is to create a big village with an urban feel. This will help in improving the quality of life of people in the rural areas and help to reduce the urban-rural divide which will ultimately reduce the rural to urban migration.

These are the major facilities includes Rurbanization.

- Skill development training along with economic activities
- Digital literacy
- Provision of fully equipped mobile health unit
- Inter-village road connectivity
- Citizen service centres

- E-gram connectivity
- Public transport facilities
- LPG gas connections
- Agro processing
- Agro services including storage and warehousing
- Sanitation facilities
- Provision of piped water supply
- Solid and liquid waste management
- Upgrading education facilities

OBJECTIVE

The objectives of the Rurbanization is to stimulate local economic development, Enhance basic services and to create well planned Rurban cluster.

This can be achieved in the three ways:

- To improve social and infrastructural development in the rural areas.
- Improving the life of people of the rural clusters bridging the rural urban divide.
- Reducing distress migration from rural to urban areas.

METHODOLOGY

In Telangana Rural people lives in 62% while urban people lives in 38%. These 62% of people major occupation is agriculture. These people lives is associated rural areas.

The study focuses this area's secondary information collected from various books, magazines, national and international journals, government reports, publication from various websites focuses on the concept of Rurbanization.

STUDY AREA

Telangana state proposed eighteen cluster to central government. The central government approved the total eighteen clusters .

The proposed clusters in Telangana are,

S.NO	CLUSTER	SUB DISTRICT	DISTRICT
1.	Allapur	Tandur	Rangareddy
2.	Ryakal	Narayanakhed	Medak
3.	Jukkal	Jukkal	Kamareddy
4.	Chirragunta	Mandamarri	Manchiryala
5.	Sarangapalle	Mandamarri	Manchiryala
6.	Vennacharla	Peddakothapally	Nagarkarnool
7.	Narlapur	Tadvai	Jayashankarbhupalapally
8.	Kuntala	Kuntala	Nirmal
9.	Kondabhimnapalle	Devarakonda	Nalgonda
10.	Choutuppal	Choutuppal	Yadadri bhuvanagiri
11.	Yedapalle	Yedapalle	Nizamabad
12.	Bijirisharif	Jammikunta	Karimnagar
13.	Papannapeta	Papannapeta	Medak
14.	Shankarpalle	Shankarpalle	Rangareddy
15.	Jaligon	Gajwel	Siddipet
16.	Nanacharla	Gandeed	Mahabubnagar
17.	Sulthanabad	Sulthanabad	Peddapally
18.	Nagaram	Bhupalapally	Bhupalapally

CONCLUSION

The development of rural areas in each and every state of India is the need of the hour. With increasing the rural to urban migration, urban cities are mostly affected due to the scarcity of resources. To mitigate the rural to urban migration and proper use of available resources in the rural areas Rurbanisation plays a key role. States like Telangana which are at early stages of development Rurbanisation serves the purpose of development in most of the rural clusters.

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